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Marcin Łączek

University of Economics and Human Sciences in Warsaw

ORCID: 0000-0001-5886-6964

Of the issues of the school as an educational and scientific institute: Cognitive Development of Bilingual Learners

Abstract

Children develop in individual ways and at varying rates – whether physically, spiritually, socially or emotionally, and language acquisition goes synchronously with cognitive and academic development. The subject of interest of the present paper are bilingualism and cognitive development of bilingual people presented through the optics of research since the pioneering studies conducted by J. Ronjat (1913) to the present times.

Key words: (applied) linguistics, bilingualism, multilingualism, immersion, submersion, cognitive development, pedagogy, social pedagogy, school, teaching

Introduction

The main objective of the present paper is to focus on cognitive advantages conferred by bilingualism. Children develop on different planes (i.e., physically, cognitively, linguistically, spiritually, socially or emotionally), in individual ways and at varying rates, and language acquisition goes synchronously with cognitive and academic development. They are born

ready to learn the language(s) of their environments without confusion or delay (J. F. Werker/K. Byers-Heinlein 2008). Perhaps one in three people is bilingual or multilingual (L. Wei 2000), which means that more than half of the world's population (more accurate estimates vary from 60 to 75 per cent) can communicate in two or more languages¹. A central issue in research on bilingual acquisition has been the nature of the child's neurocognitive or linguistic representation of his developing languages. It was argued that children exposed to two languages go through an initial stage when the languages are not differentiated: the most explicit formulation of this hypothesis was proposed by V. Volterra and T. Taeschner (1978).

Bilingualism: Definition and Typology

Although many a definition exists in the literature on bilingualism, they are quite convergent indeed (bearing in mind the effusion of mixed contexts and reference points). It is not the intention, nor would it be possible in a short publication like this to review all of them – let me just refer to a few: “the native-like control of two languages” (L. Bloomfield 1933:56)², the production of “complete and meaningful utterances in other languages” (E. Haugen 1953:6), “the practice of alternately using two languages” (U.

¹ According to G. R. Tucker (1998), there may be as many (or even more) children who grow up bilingual as monolingual. Many countries have more than one official national language, too – the most prominent example being South Africa with the astonishing number of eleven (G. Vince 2016).

² The full text of L. Bloomfield's (1933: 55-56) definition of bilingualism reads: “[i]n the extreme case of foreign-language learning the speaker becomes so proficient as to be indistinguishable from the native speakers round him. This happens occasionally in adult shifts of language and frequently in the childhood shifts just described. In the cases where this perfect foreign-language learning is not accompanied by loss of the native language, it results in bilingualism, native-like control of two languages. After early childhood few people have enough muscular and nervous freedom or enough opportunity and leisure to reach perfection in a foreign language; yet bilingualism of this kind is commoner than one might suppose, both in cases like those of our immigrants and as a result of travel, foreign study or similar association. Of course, one cannot define a degree of perfection at which a good foreign speaker becomes a bilingual: the distinction is relative.”

Weinreich 1953:1), “simultaneous learning of two languages from infancy” (S. Arsenjan 1954: 81). A question of both the first and the second language expertise level can be posed: i.e., does one talk of bilingualism when two well-developed and roughly equal fluencies are experienced only? Or, as C. Baker (1988: 2) puts it, “[a] pupil may be able to understand spoken English and Welsh, speak English fluently but Welsh only haltingly, read in Welsh with a reading age of six and in English with a reading age of eight, write poorly in English and not at all in Welsh. Is that pupil bilingual?” As we have been able to see, L. Bloomfield (1933) and U. Weinreich (1953) were content to remain vague in this respect, while E. Haugen (1953) suggested that linguistic repertoire expansion begins with the ability to produce complete and meaningful utterances in a second language. Without any doubt, earlier definitions were more restrictive in their nature with more recent ones allowing more room for greater variation in competence.

Researchers generally consider a child to be bilingual if he receives from ten to twenty-five per cent of exposure to each language (V. A. Marchman et al. 2004, V. A. Marchman et al. 2010, S. Place/ E. Hoff 2011, K. Byers-Heinlein 2013), but this level of exposure by no means guarantees functional bilingualism (A. De Houwer 2007). Research has also proved that both monolingual and bilingual children can best show off their skills when using language that matches their daily experiences (K. Mattock et al. 2010). Still though, E. Lipińska (2013: 133) believes, bilingualism is not measured, it is just assumed to exist; what can be measured is the mastery of the initial and target languages only: the tests used to measure bilingualism can include rating scales and tests of fluency, flexibility, and dominance. The first of these can involve interviews, language-usage measures or self-assessment procedures, and these personal reports have a lot to recommend them. Their strengths, however, rest upon the ability (and

willingness) to self-report accurately, and a roughly equivalent sense across informants of what competence actually is (J. Edwards 2013).

Bilingualism can be experienced in many different contexts, that is it can be both endo- and exolingual environment-embedded. Its typology is broad alike: active, additive, adult, ascendant, balanced, bimodal, circumstantial, coexistent, cognitive, collective, complementary, complete/ full, compound, consecutive, coordinate, dominant, dormant, elective, élite, family, folk, functional, group, imperfect, incipient, individual, majority, merged, minority, natural, passive, perfect, primary, productive, real, receptive, recessive, replacive, restricted, secondary, sequential, simultaneous, social, social psychological, societal, subordinate, subtractive, successive, symmetric or transitional – these are examples of the most commonly found attributes only for the above list is by no means complete (U. Weinreich 1953, S. Ervin/ C. Osgood 1954, E.S. Klima/ U. Bellugi 1979, F. Grosjean 1982, K. Hakuta et. al 1987, S. Döpke 1992, B. Spolsky 1998, C. Baker/ S. P. Jones 1998, E. Bialystok 2001, P. Ó Riagáin/ G. Lüdi 2003, T. K. Bhatia/ W. C. Ritchie 2004, A. Lam 2006, E. Peal/ W. E. Lambert 2007, E. Lipińska/ A. Seretny 2012, C. Baker 2011, J. Bloemendal 2015).³

Cognitive Development of Bilingual Learners

Research on infant bilingualism in the “one person – one language” environment was extensively carried out by linguists observing their own children (J. Ronjat 1913, W. F. Leopold 1939–49, D. C. Porsché 1983, T. Taeschner 1983, B. Kielhöfer/ S. Jonekeit 1983, C. Hoffmann 1985, G. Saunders 1988 or H. Kravin 1992) as well as non-linguist parents (L. Arnberg 1981/ 1987, E. Harding/ P. Riley 1986, S. Döpke 1992)⁴. It was the French

³ See, for example, M. Łączek (2018) for further clarification and the literature quoted therein.

⁴ Criticism against research on childhood bilingualism under the “one person – one language” principle was voiced by, for instance, S. Romaine (1995) or J. Lyon (1996). In a similar tone, S. Döpke (1998) claimed that the “‘one parent–one language’ principle at the more rigid end of the monolingual – bilingual continuum is superior to less rigid language choice patterns”,

psychologist J. Ronjat who was an author of the first study on, what has been termed, bilingual first language acquisition. The said study, published in 1913, was carried out in Paris, and involved J. Ronjat's detailed records of his son Louis' speech at different stages of his life – that is from his birth to the age of four years and ten months. During this experiment, the child was exclusively addressed in the mother tongue of the father, that is the French language (by his father), and German – the native language of the mother (by his mother as well as his nanny). Louis showed remarkable progress in both these languages and little sign of confusion, which made J. Ronjat (1913) formulate an overall constative that his bilingual upbringing had no detrimental effects on his cognitive development and that lexis, phonology or grammar developed alongside one another. What is more, Louis eventually realised that there were two separate languages, which, when necessary, even made him act as an interpreter⁵.

W. F. Leopold conducted his studies during the years 1939-1949; with the publication (1949) of the last volume, which included a detailed diary of his daughter Hildegard's simultaneous acquisition of English and German, J. Ronjat's (1913) viewpoint seemed to have been brought into doubt (the study, in general, involved the linguistic development of his two daughters under the "one person – one language" rule)⁶. But structured approaches, such as using different languages as a function of person can include a place function alike (that is: one language at home, one language outside)

adding that there are three aspects when it comes to how far this rigidity should go with respect to using the minority language beyond the home: quantity of input, topics one talks about, and the people one talks with.

⁵ Research proved that bilingual children can produce translation equivalents from the time they first begin to speak (B. Z. Pearson et al. 1995) or by 8 months on (S. Quay 1995, F. Genesee et al. 1995b, E. Nicoladis/ F. Genesee 1996, E. Nicoladis 1998, M. Deuchar/S. Quay 2000).

⁶ For a follow-up study to further examine young bilingual children's ability to differentiate their languages see F. Genesee et al. (1996).

or a time factor, too (alternating days of the week, or times within the day: mornings versus afternoons); more than that, there are parents who insist on speaking only one language with their child even if they are able to communicate in the other language (E. Lanza 1997/ 2004). F. Genesee et al. (1995a) noticed such a dependency: when the parents were together with the child, the child used significantly more of the mother's language with the mother than with the father, and more of the father's language with the father than with the mother – that, in turn, proved that the child's language use was context-sensitive, which was an argument for functional differentiation of languages.

Coming back to W. F. Leopold's studies (1939-1949), Hildegard passed through a stage when she used words from both languages, a fact that he interpreted as a sign of her confusing the two languages and, consequently, functioning as a monolingual; the overall results (as well as conclusions) were comparable to J. Ronjat's (1913), however. That children exposed to two languages go through an initial stage when those languages are not differentiated was an assumption of the unitary language system hypothesis (W. F. Leopold 1949, V. Volterra/T. Taeschner 1978). Contrary to the claims of the hypothesis in question, as proved by A. De Houwer (1990), M. Deuchar and S. Quay (2000), J. Meisel (2001) or F. Genesee (2001), BFL learners do acquire language-specific properties of the target languages early in development and these correspond to those exhibited by same-age monolingual children.

Subsequent studies by W. Penfield and W. E. Lambert (E. Peal/ W. E. Lambert 1962) confirmed that bilingual children do not differ at all from their monolingual peers, except that they know two languages, and not one (W. Klein 1986). Such implications (E. Peal/ W. E. Lambert 1962) proved positive effect of bilingual education on the child's native language, intelligence, and cognitive functioning: bilinguals outperform monolinguals in a range of cognitive and social tasks. The said experiments (E. Peal/ W. E. Lambert

1962) also tested bilingual children's creativity level with the help of the tasks which asked them to invent other uses for ordinary objects – their outcome confirmed that in more complex tasks the bilinguals performed better.

E. Bialystok (2005) addressed this extra positive benefit, and surmised that since bilinguals possess two language systems, every notion in their minds has, as a consequence, two different names. That in turn helps them develop abilities to perceive the same thing from two different perspectives and to, as she put it, “switch” freely between the notions in question. Indeed, bilingual children show a special objective awareness of language (which ultimately contributed to the formulation of objectification hypothesis); according to it, their objectification of language is conducive to higher levels of abstract and symbolic thinking – bilingual children have two words for each referent (W. F. Leopold 1949). In a similar vein, L. S. Vygotsky (1962: 110) advised that since bilinguals can express the same thought in different languages, the bilingual child is able to “see his language as one particular system among many, to view its phenomena under more general categories” as well as possess “an awareness of his linguistic operations”. Finally, A.V. Kharkhurin (2007) challenged the assumption that the relation between creativity and bilingualism is so obvious: the results of his empirical research showed that bilingualism can affect divergent thinking (i.e., the basic component of creative thinking). Further he (2007) argued that if there was any significant relationship between bilingualism and creativity, naturally multilingual countries should have the highest number of people with creative thinking abilities, which by no means has been confirmed so far. A. V. Kharkhurin (2007) did conclude, however, that bilingualism seemed to have had a positive impact on divergent thinking. Therefore, it is worth supporting bilingual education of a child although there are other factors

influencing the development of creativity, too, such as: intelligence, education, motivation and personal experience.

D. Marsh et al. (2009) took a slightly different approach and made an analysis of the scientific literature (both European and international) in order to assess what impact multilingualism actually has on the development of creativity. The research in question was carried out in all 27 European Union member states plus Norway and Turkey; there were five main hypotheses formulated: 1) there is a link between multilingualism and creativity; 2) multilingualism broadens access to information; 3) multilingualism offers alternative ways of organizing thoughts; 4) multilingualism offers alternative ways of perceiving the world around us; 5) learning a new language increases the possibilities for creative thinking. The results of the study in question (2009) indicated that it is difficult to establish a direct causal relationship between the two – yet it is very likely that multilingualism positively influences creative thinking skills (this advantage was identified as the key to economic and social success in the “knowledge society”). The tangible benefits that help bilinguals cope more efficiently in social life, according to D. Marsh et al. (2009), are: a) mental flexibility, b) ability to solve problems, c) better developed metalinguistic abilities, d) ability to learn to create new solutions from the acquired information, e) ability to build deeper interpersonal relationships, or f) the fact that they mentally age two to four years later⁷.

⁷ Cf. the research by E. Bialystok et al. (2007) on the protective effect of bilingualism on dementia or F. Craik et al.'s (2010). According to the latter, although bilingualism does not prevent Alzheimer's disease or other types of dementia, it might promote the formation of cognitive reserves in the brain that have seemed to delay the symptoms of the disease significantly. More than that, by learning an additional language, a person trains the most important parts of the brain, including the prefrontal cortex where the process of switching the executive function occurs (E. Bialystok 2011). Finally, when a bilingual person hears a word, his brain starts to navigate between the two language systems to figure out what it means, in what context to put it, and how to react to it, which eventually contributes to bilinguals being perceived as multitaskers (F. Craik et al. 2010).

Most studies on the positive impact of bilingualism on brain activity have been conducted on children: T. Bajo (2011) reported that bilingualism improves the endurance and abilities of the brain, because the mind learns to set aside those abilities that are not immediately used. The fact that monolingual children lose the abilities that bilinguals manage to retain (because they are constantly making use of them) was recognised by J. Werker (2011) alike. It, namely, turned out that 8-month-old children raised in monolingual (Spanish or Catalan) and bilingual (Spanish and Catalan) families lost interest in the person who spoke the same language (either English or French), but when that person started using a different language the child became interested again since that meant something new and/ or interesting to him. What is of significance here: the child realized that the language had changed only by carefully observing the speaker's facial movements (the children watched a video recording only, with no sound) – through rhythms and articulation observance (J. Werker 2011).

M. Paradis (2000, 2004) demonstrated that, in qualitative terms, the brain of the monolingual person is no different from the brain of the bilingual person: any differences are only a consequence of the degree to which the brain's potential is used. The bilingual is not the sum of two monolinguals either (F. Grosjean 1989) for “bilinguals (and multilinguals) have a unique form of language competence that is not necessarily comparable to that of monolinguals because learning a second or additional language has an influence on the whole cognitive system. Second language users possess unique forms of competence, or competencies, in their own right” (J. Cenoz 2008: 27). In fact, children acquiring two languages simultaneously demonstrated to have possessed differentiated systems that were generally the same as those of children acquiring the same languages monolingually; cross-language influences, or transfers, were found (although at times restricted and temporary only in both space and time) by A. Hulk and E. Van

Der Linden (1996), N. Müller (1998), S. Döpke (2000) or V. Yip and S. J. Matthews (2000).⁸ That said, code-mixing should not be treated as a sign that the bilingual is unable to keep his languages apart but, rather, as a manifestation of a unique multicultural personality: he is able to communicate with people from different language groups and cultures even though the monolingual speaker might possess a larger vocabulary span in one language (C. Baker 2000). The code-mixing hypothesis, first proposed by E. Peal and W. E. Lambert (1962) as an explanatory hypothesis to their pioneer findings, refers to the observation that bilinguals can move from one language to the other with relative ease. More over, code-mixing among bilingual children proved to be grammatically constrained since children tend to mix the two languages whose grammar is concordant; grammatical constraints on intra-utterance code-mixing were investigated by J. Meisel (1994), E. Lanza (1997/ 2004), M. Vihman (1998), D. Sauvre and F. Genesee (2000) or J. Paradis et al. (2000), just to name a few. Contrary to initial assumptions, it was pointed out, adult bilinguals also code-mix: research on adult bilinguals carried out by, among others, S. Poplack (1980), C. Myers-Scotton (1993/ 1997) or J. MacSwan (1999) indicated that code-mixing within an utterance or sentence is not random but, rather, grammatically constrained (in accordance with the morpho-syntactic properties of the participating languages).

When it comes to differences in vocabulary size in each language, these were attributable to differences in the frequency of exposure (B. Z. Pearson et al. 1997); bilingual children receive primary input in each

⁸ Code-mixing (as opposed to code-switching), whether intra- or inter-utterance mixing, is understood as the use of elements (phonological, morphosyntactic or lexical) from two languages in the same utterance or stretch of conversation. According to R. M. Diaz and R. Padilla (1985), language switching is a social and not an intrapersonal cognitive phenomenon; at least in bilingual preschoolers. For bilingual children's ability to repair breakdowns in communication due to their use of language dispreferred by their interlocutor see, e.g., L. Comeau/ F. Genesee (2001).

language from different interlocutors, therefore, they may acquire different lexical repertoires for different people talk about different subjects (A. De Houwer 1990). A study which aimed to answer the question of whether bilingual children learn as many words as their monolingual peers was conducted by D. Poulin Dubois et al. (2011). The researchers (2011) confirmed that by the age of two bilingual children not only have a vocabulary range similar to that of their monolingual peers (and have learnt to switch – at least to some extent) from one language to another, but are also able to focus more successfully on tasks when deliberately distracted. To take a different example, V. Volterra and T. Taeschner (1978) surmised that children exposed to two languages go through an initial stage when the languages are not differentiated; such differentiated linguistic systems only emerge in three stages: “[i]n the first stage the child has one lexical system which includes words from both languages. (...) in this stage the language development of the bilingual child seems to be like the language development of the monolingual child. (...) In the second stage, the child distinguishes two different lexicons, but applies the same syntactic rules to both languages. In the third stage the child speaks two languages differentiated both in lexicon and syntax (...)” (V. Volterra/T. Taeschner 1978: 312).⁹Last but not least, W. Lazaruk (2007) in his research on the outcomes of immersion education noticed that there exists a gap between reception and production skills, and set out a range of cognitive benefits of bilingualism to which he included divergent thinking, mental flexibility, communicative sensitivity or metalinguistic awareness. He (2007) also contributed to the assumptions of a neurolinguistic theory of bilingualism by establishing that bilingual learners understand their second language directly and not through the medium of

⁹ That bilingual children go through a monolingual stage was also suggested by W. F. Leopold (1939-1949).

their mother tongue, the fact which resulted in a conclusion that there exist two language sub-systems interacting with a single non-linguistic system.

While bilingual children might typically know fewer words in each of the languages¹⁰, the range of their “conceptual vocabulary” across both languages is greater for sure (V. A. Marchman et al. 2010). Bilingual infants, in a study by A.M. Kovács and J. Mehler (2009), revealed to have possessed better memory and concentration spans (when prompted to associate a specific word with the appearance of a toy). And not to mention that in conversational abilities they were actually able to match monolinguals (L. Comeau et al. 2010): when somebody used a confusing or mispronounced word or said something ambiguous, bilingual children repaired such a conversation to their advantage. Bearing the above in mind, bilingualism was at times indeed in correctly associated with delays in cognitive development, the symptoms of which included worse performance at school, for instance. As already indicated, however, the total vocabulary size or the length of mixed utterances produced by bilingual children are by no means smaller/shorter compared to those of monolingual children: their monolingual utterances just happen to be poorer sometimes (S. Romaine 1999). Bilinguals are relatively more creative and more imaginative in their thinking, too (C. Baker 2000).

Bilinguals show many cognitive advantages, which has been proved by studies carried out not only among bilingual adults (A. Costa et al. 2008) or children (E. Bialystok/ M. M. Martin 2004), but also infants (Á. M. Kovács/J. Mehler 2009) and toddlers (P. Poulin-Dubois et al. 2011). Although the bilingual’s two languages may influence each other to a certain degree (S. Döpke 2000), when it comes to their development in many ways they are independent; that is to say: bilingual children who hear a large amount of a

¹⁰ According to B. Z. Pearson et al. (1993) or B. Z. Pearson/ S. C. Fernández (1994), bilingual children know approximately the same number of words as monolingual children.

particular language learn more words and grammar in that language (B. Z. Pearson/S. C. Fernández 1994, E. Hoff et al. 2012), and show more efficient processing of that language (B. T. Conboy, D. L. Mills 2006, V. A. Marchman et al. 2010, N. Hurtado et al. 2013). In addition to that, they appear to perform better, compared to monolinguals, on tasks involving switching between activities and inhibiting previously learnt responses (E. Bialystok et al. 2012). Lastly, there exists evidence that bilingual infants are advantaged in certain aspects of memory, such as generalizing information from one event to a later event (N. Brito/R. Barr 2012).¹¹

J. Bourne (2002) recognized the significance of home languages in bilingual upbringing and education for: a) they enhance children's cognitive and language development by increasing their understanding of how spoken and written language works, b) they enhance their success in learning additional languages, c) they enhance their overall levels of attainment as well as improve their metalinguistic awareness; there is no threat of loss of the first language in the case of additive bilingualism since the child's attitude towards his own language and culture – as well as foreign – is positive (W. E. Lambert 1974). As a matter of fact, a series of more recent studies on bilingual children have shown that bilingualism can represent a strong stimulus to the child's intellectual development (R. Laskowski 2014). According to J. F. Hamers and M. H. A. Blanc (1990: 78), positive cognitive consequences are almost invariably associated with positive parental attitudes towards both languages and literacy: "(...) it appears clearly that early bilingual experience enhances cognitive functioning when the child has the opportunity to develop all functions of language and provided that both languages are highly valorized." It is in subtractive bilingualism that one's

¹¹ At the same time, it is important to note that bilingualism is not the only kind of experience that has been linked to cognitive advantages – these were also observed in individuals with early musical training (E. G. Schellenberg 2005).

mother tongue becomes absorbed by the second language, which eventually might lead to the former's loss (W. E. Lambert 1974). Mindful of that, relatively balanced exposure to the two languages is most likely to promote their successful acquisition (E. Thordardottir 2011) although it does not by any means guarantee later bilingualism, even if provided in the early years. In fact, minority languages learnt in preschool are much more likely to be lost as development continues than majority languages (A. De Houwer 2007). More than that, as children get older interacting with monolingual speakers (especially other children) is important for motivating ongoing language use, especially for minority languages not widely spoken in the community. Hence the recommendation to provide, wherever possible, more early input in a minority language (B. Z. Pearson 2008).¹²

Conclusions

As we have been able to note throughout the course of the present paper despite the early work of J. Ronjat (1913) and W. F. Leopold (1939-1949) further research remained considerably sparse until the 1980s. It was only towards the end of the previous century that there was an upsurge in attention devoted to bilingual acquisition, including research on the relation between bilingualism and cognitive development conducted, among others, by: S. E. Duncan and E. A. De Avila (1979) who attempted to examine the effects of bilingualism using a "within-bilingual" design, B. Bain and A. Yu (1980) who concluded that balanced bilingual children outperform their monolingual peers in their capacity to use language to monitor cognitive performance, K. Hakuta and R. M. Diaz (1985), R. M. Diaz (1985) or R. M. Diaz and K. Padilla (1985) – all of whom took the multiple regression approach in order to investigate the effects of bilingualism in preschoolers,

¹² Older children and adults often find themselves in a classroom where they get a small fraction of the language practice that infants and toddlers do (C. Lew-Williams/ A. Fernald 2010).

kindergarten children, and first-grade children attending bilingual education programs; significant contributions of second-language proficiency on cognitive development were duly reported.¹³

Contrary to J. Cummins's (1976) threshold hypothesis which recognizes that linguistic and cognitive development occurs within a sociocultural context, and which predicts positive effects of bilingualism at high levels of second-language attainment, the data obtained by R. M. Diaz (1985) suggest that bilingualism may have a stronger effect on cognitive abilities for children who are at the beginning stages of second-language learning. R. Appel and P. Muysken (1987) were cautious, however, as per the beneficial effect of bilingualism on the child's cognitive development and emphasised the crucial role of social factors, saying that it is not bilingualism per se that is of fundamental importance to the child's intellectual development, but, rather, the social setting in which the two languages are acquired. According to them (1987) bilingualism can be a stimulating factor for the child's intellectual development on condition that his competence in both languages attains a certain threshold level; otherwise, the child's imperfect bilingualism or, more accurately, semilingualism, might cause delays in his cognitive development. The concept of the "balanced" bilingual child was conceived yet by E. Peal and W. E. Lambert (1962) in an attempt to distinguish "pseudobilinguals" from truly bilingual children – in doing so they (1962) shifted the definition of bilingualism from the societal plane to the cognitive one.

Research on language development in bilingual children has contributed to a better understanding of the entire pattern of language development in all children, including those with disorders. Frequent delays in

¹³ Many studies were devoted to metalinguistic awareness of learners, see, e.g., A. Ianco-Worrall (1972), S. Ben-Zeev (1977) or J. Cummins (1978).

language acquisition by these children have sometimes been mistaken for specific language impairment (SLI), which also occurs in monolingual children. Still, few clinicians receive quality training about the learning needs of bilingual children, which in some cases may lead to a misdiagnosis of bilingual children as having delayed or disordered language (E. Thordardottir et al. 2006, L. Bedore/E. Peña 2008, K. Kohnert 2010). Bilingual children, as has been widely indicated in the literature on the subject, prove no more likely than monolingual children to have difficulties with language, to show delays in learning or to be diagnosed with language disorders (L. A. Petitto/ S. Holowka 2002, J. Paradis et al. 2010); bilingual children with specific language impairments (J. Paradis et al. 2003), Down syndrome (E. Kay-Raining Bird et al. 2005), and autism spectrum disorders (J. M. Petersen et al. 2012) are not more likely to experience any additional delays or challenges compared to monolingual children with these impairments either.

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